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PERSONAL CAPITAL OF TOURISM SPHERE: STATE, CHALLENGES AND TRENDS OF DEVELOPMENT

The article outlines and substantiates the state and trends of the personnel potential in tourism sphere formation. It is proved that in order to optimize the development of a competitive human resources potential of the tourism sector in Ukraine, it is necessary to predict and plan the need for personnel, to select and allocate personnel in accordance with the competence level, to create an effective personnel reserve, to plan personnel development, to form and implement a motivational component. It has been characterized that effective human resources policy in the field of tourism of Ukraine should facilitate the professional growth of specialists, ensuring self-realization and the success of professional activity. The necessity of initiative, competent personnel with a new style of thinking and vision of the development of the tourism environment, possessing democratic methods of management, an ability to act in the current conditions of social development, being open to the introduction of relevant innovations, which will ensure the formation of competitive personnel potential in the search for a new paradigm in the sphere of tourism in Ukraine is substantiated. On the basis of the results of the study, a number of practical recommendations were developed for the purpose of realization and implementation of effective human resources management of a tourism enterprise in Ukraine.

Keywords: personnel potential, success, professional activity, specialist-tourism expert, human resources, competitive expert, self-realization, competence approach, sphere of tourism.

Introduction. In modern conditions, the tourism industry is in urgent need of specialists with a high level of professional competence, non-standard thinking, which is characterized by creativity and creative problems solving approach. Such specialists are fundamentally different from the «previous generation» of specialists in the field of tourism, when it was simply enough for the expert to perform a certain established algorithm of work. That is why the modern process of personnel potential formation and development in the tourism sphere of Ukraine should be based on the improvement of the future specialist-tourism experts, on the manifestations and prospects of their creative potential, and professional activity is carried out on the basis of innovative methods and practices implementation that will ensure their competitiveness in the labor market.

The urgency of the topic is confirmed by an express survey on the necessity of forming and developing a competitive human resources potential of the tourist environment.

Analysis of recent research. The essence and functional role of human resources forming of tourism sphere in their scientific developments were considered by L. Knodel, N. Stepanets, T. Tkachenko, V. Tolkovanov, I. Tregulov, I. Shcogoleva, V. Fedorchenko and others. Scientists and practitioners analyzed the concept of «human resource», the management of the professionalization of tourism personnel, the training of specialists in tourism, the formation of professional competence and disability. However, the scientific literature has not yet fully analyzed and substantiated the issue of human resources development in the search for a new paradigm in the field of tourism. This is what substantiates the relevance of the article.

Unresolved parts of the general problem are finding out the state, challenges and trends of human resource development in the tourism sector of Ukraine.

The purpose of this research is to provide scientific and practical comprehension and substantiation of trends in the development of personnel capacity building in the tourism sector of Ukraine.

The scientific novelty of the article is in theoretical improving and practical research of professional activity and in substantiating the ways of the development of human resources optimizing in the field of tourism of Ukraine.

Presenting main material. In the conditions of a modern market economy, for the successful development of the tourism sector, recreational resources, capital, innovative technologies and, most importantly, competitive personnel potential are needed. As the scientists point out, «... talented, skilled, experienced specialists – this is not only a resource that can effectively achieve the goals, but also a source of competitive advantage» (Ivanova, 2008). The concept of human resources should be considered in the context of the «potential» concept in general. In this case, the human potential is the ability of a certain category of personnel, specialists, and other groups of workers that can be put into action in the course of work in accordance with the official duties and strategic objectives of the tourist enterprise at the present stage of development.

Thus, potential is a possibility that, realized in activity, is perfected, while remaining potential (Mitina, 2002, p. 15). Potential of personality – the ability of a person to increase their internal capabilities, first of all – the ability to develop; the ability to live a rich inner life and to effectively interact with the environment, to be productive, to manipulate effectively, to grow successfully to develop competitiveness. That is, the potential in the field of tourism – is the available resources of a specialist and the ability to use them rationally. Such approach to the definition of human resources provides an opportunity for a comprehensive analysis of any category of personnel on the basis of objective economic laws in accordance with the chosen object, subject of the study, as well as its goals and objectives (Mitina, 2002; The CMU Order dated

March 16, 2017). Personnel potential of the enterprise should be considered as a general (quantitative and qualitative) characteristic of the personnel, as one of the types of resources, associated with the implementation of its assigned functions and the achievement of the goals of the long-term enterprise development; these are the available and potential capabilities of employees as a holistic system (team) that are used and can be used at a certain time (Busel, 2005, p. 1567). Note that specialists-tourists of the new paradigm put people's interests in the first place, preferring: changes, rather than stability; power transfer, rather than control; co-operation on rivalry; diversity, rather than homogeneity; honesty over personal gain. In the context of the foregoing, let us note that it is a specialist in tourism with a high level of leadership potential, professional competence and competitiveness.

Today, practice shows that modern Ukrainian society is characterized by a complex and controversial changes in the model of human potential. That is why the most important strategic goals of personnel policy development in tourism sphere are the restoration of human resources, intellectual potential and its maximum realization.

In light of the above, the priority directions of human potential development in the tourism sphere of Ukraine should be singled out, namely:

- stimulation of highly skilled labor, innovative activities, science-intensive products, resource-saving technologies;
- the transition in management systems from the domination of theories of classical management to the concepts of human capital;
- creation of a nationwide information system «Personnel», which would enable to ensure effective personnel policy;
- support of creativity in all kinds of production, scientific, cultural and educational activities;
- introduction into the practice of production of information technologies, total computerization of society;
- material and moral support for talented youth (Armstrong, 2004, p. 104-105).

At the same time, it should be emphasized that the human potential in real terms may be represented by the capabilities of tourism specialists, the quality of their professional qualification training, professional, personal, psychological and physiological qualities, as well as, most importantly, creative and creative abilities (Armstrong, 2004, p. 11-25). We are convinced that the human resources management system of tourist enterprises should be formed from an analysis of the existing personnel potential; on the choice of actions, in accordance with the general strategy of the tourist enterprise, regarding the development, preservation or restructuring of the personnel; the creation of organizational culture; introduction and implementation of innovative techniques and technologies; from complex control, assessment of personnel potential and ensuring the success of professional staffing.

Currently, the management system for the development of human resources in the sphere of tourism requires the implementation of changes,

bringing them in line with international standards, where priority development should be given to the improvement of leadership potential of specialists in the field of tourism, the formation of a successful and competitive specialist. In this case, special attention should be given to the theory of human resources, which is based on understanding of personnel as a set of tools, stocks, sources, which have the ability to be accumulated and implemented in order to ensure the success of professional activities.

Analyzing the scientific literature, we can note that personnel policy defines the main content of the staff selection, placement, training and retraining program. In general terms, human resources policy should be interpreted as an integrated system of theoretical knowledge, ideas and installations of a tourism enterprise, aimed at establishing a strategy, principles and priorities for the management and effective forms and methods of personnel activities to ensure the development of human resources capacity in the tourism sector.

The basis of the human potential formation of tourism specialists is a well-defined system of concrete measures for the selection, training and professional activity of specialists, based on the principles of integrity, universality, scientific validity, consistency, accessibility and openness, as well as the balance of personal and professional interests with an orientation towards long-term perspective and the need for their proper legislative support.

Effective development of the tourism industry is impossible without competent specialists, professionals, who have critical thinking, creativity and innovation. We are convinced that the use of tourism potential is practically impossible without scientific and personnel support.

Thus, as stated in the Tourism Development and Resorts Development Strategy for the period up to 2026, the main directions of the Strategy implementation in the area of «Human Resource Development» are:

- improvement of the specialists professional training system in the tourism and resorts sphere and other areas related to tourism, which will help to increase the level of professional training of specialists in the field of tourism and resorts and the quality of service of consumers of tourist services through:

- comprehensive study of the labor market in the field of tourism and resorts in order to identify the need for specialists in the relevant profile, developing the appropriate basic competencies of specialists and preparing educational programs for vocational training in tourism and resorts, taking into account the identified needs;

- harmonization of qualification requirements and higher education standards in higher education institutions providing training in tourism and resorts, and standards for vocational training;

- approval of qualification requirements for specialists of tourist support;

- provision of scientific support and research in the field of tourism and resorts, introduction of progressive innovative developments through;

– encouraging young people to work actively, developing innovative products and starting a business in tourism and resorts based on the results of competitions at the regional and sectoral level (The CMU Order dated March 16. 2017).

Taking into account the aforementioned, in order to level the negative tendencies in the modern approach of effective management realization of the tourist enterprise personnel resources, it is expedient to distinguish such tasks as: implementation of effective management activity; formation of a new generation of personnel for tourism; promotion of the personnel potential and achievement of successful professional activity; use of innovative technologies of planning, motivation and evaluation of personnel; formation of partnership conditions of employees and management, etc. It is the tasks that will ensure a multifunctional process of human resources for the formation, development and rational use of personnel in tourism.

In the general sense the effective personnel policy formation of a tourist enterprise, the priority task of which is to manage the personnel resources of a tourist enterprise in Ukraine efficiently, should be based on the following objectives: forecasting and planning of the tourist enterprise personnel needs (quantitative and qualitative provision of the organization by the relevant personnel);

- personnel development planning, permanent postgraduate education, advanced training;
- development of criteria and methods of selection, placement, assessment and training of personnel;
- motivation of employees, that is, ensuring personal interest of employees of any level in achieving high results of work;
- influence on the improvement of the management style, the development of certain socially significant stereotypes of behavior.

We emphasize that stimulating the potential development of specialists in the sphere of tourism is undoubtedly the key to the prosperity of the tourist enterprise, the formation of a positive image and reputation and the achievement of competitiveness in the service market.

Priority in the formation and implementation of effective human resources capacity in the tourism sphere should be given to real and effective planning of professional development of personnel, which ensures the success of professional activity and the formation of a motivational component for the assurance of a professional future. It should be noted that the management of the personnel of the modern tourism business should now be based on a model of career management, which is defined as «person-position-person». The indicated model provides for the initial determination of the potential of a tourism specialists and their reasons for professional activity, the search for positions they will be able to occupy in the course of their careers, the definition of requirements for these positions, the development of positions professional competence profiles, professional-business, political and personal qualities.

Important in this context is the ability of specialists in the field of tourism to increase constantly the level of professional knowledge. It should be noted that the effective forms of professional development tourist specialist need to include: training in professional training programs; thematic workshops; master classes, trainings; internship abroad and so on. Among the various forms and areas of work that contribute to the enhancement of professional competence, a special place is occupied by educational activities and self-education (Ivanova, 2008, p. 50-58). It is also important to take into account the importance of continuous improvement, guided by the principle of «life-long learning».

It is clear that professional development is the paradigm that leads to the creation of individual and personal professionalism in the tourist business environment. It includes the degree of compliance with the requirements of professional activity and capacity; a dynamic indicator that is a litmus test paper for the formation of competitiveness and a combination of specific content and activity criteria in accordance with the laws of the person's integration into professional activity (Busel, 2005, p. 15-20). Thus, professional development of personnel is the basic basis for forming competitive personnel potential of tourism sphere of Ukraine.

Primary role in shaping the competitive leadership potential of tourism personnel needs to be diverted from the use of appropriate principles, such as human centeredness, adult education principles, portfolio orientation competencies, leadership development, capacity development, self-realization, positive thinking, partnership and dialogicity, critical thinking, innovation and the success of a professional activity.

At the same time, the key to the success of professional activity of specialists-tourist researchers is the selection and achievement of goals. We consider that the main purpose of professional activity of a specialist in tourism is professional self-realization, professional growth and achievement of success. Thus, the main purpose of a tourist specialist is to realize himself as a professional, step by step achieving success in professional activity. Accordingly, the strategic objectives in achieving the goals of the specialist can be defined as follows: goal orientation, initiative, innovation and professional competence.

Taking into account the above, we propose a strategy for the purpose of a tourism specialist professional activity to determine by such an algorithm: «the definition of goals → achievement of goals in professional activities → the implementation of the planned strategy of success → evaluation of the results of the activities → the success of professional activities of a specialist in the field of tourism». Consequently, the personnel potential formation of a modern type in the field of tourism is based on rational use of personality traits, satisfaction of needs, creating conditions for the formation of a new type of specialist – professional, competent, able to act in an innovative, creative, initiative and creative way, to achieve the success of professional activity.

Analyzing the data of our express survey, we note that the respondents singled out a complex of competencies necessary for the formation of professional competences of a successful specialist in the tourism sphere.

In particular, the definition of the activity and vision direction; effective communication; decency and justice; delegation of authority; strategic thinking; making managerial decisions; analytical thinking; skills of working with information; innovation; knowledge of socio-political and economic trends of Ukrainian society development; leadership; professional experience; improvement of activity; change management; strictness; time management; ability to perform the most of their own abilities; stress management; self-confidence, decisions taken; ability to work in a team; creativity; critical thinking; responsibility; self improvement; organizational skills; trust; conflict management; rational resource management; customer orientation and targeting.

Thus, the basic principles of the formation and development of human resources in the tourism sector are the possession of the appropriate competencies necessary for a high level of competitive expertise in the field of tourism. We are convinced that the model of professional competences of a competitive tourism specialist is formed on the basis of universal and professional competencies. At the same time, we will refer to universal ones: general sciences (basic knowledge of the exact, humanitarian, natural sciences), instrumental (computer skills, written and oral communication); social and personal; to professional – general-professional, basic theoretical knowledge and skills, practical competences, profile and special, academic knowledge and skills, professional knowledge and competencies.

The basis of the foregoing is the formation of personnel potential on the basis of a competent approach and taking into account social order. At the same time, it should be as much as possible aimed at future professional needs, to form a level of professional and general culture, professional competence that will allow maintaining high professionalism at the level of growing demands of society, professional corporation, consumers of tourism.

Taking into consideration the analysis of scientific literature, normative legal acts and the results of a sociological survey, we consider it's expedient to propose «a portfolio of competences for the success of human resources in the sphere of tourism». In the general sense, the concept of «portfolio» is understood as a catalog of important documents, a collection of achievements that embody the most important achievements of a specialist; as a way of recording and storing materials. We believe that this is a business card that gives an idea of a successful tourist specialist and the opportunity to make a qualitative assessment of the result, to build a further plan of action. The structure of the proposed portfolio includes the conceptual, professional, strategic, personal, communicative, cognitive and effective spheres of competence, which forms the basis of the success formation of professional human resources activity in the field of tourism.

The conceptual foundations of the spheres are a list of the necessary professional activities in the field of tourism. In particular:

– the conceptual sphere of competencies (the desire for perfect management, the involvement of specialists in management, the

demonstration of the values of tourism, the management of innovations and changes in the field of tourism, knowledge and compliance with the legal and regulatory framework of tourism business);

- professional competence (professional higher education, possession of moral and ethical principles and their use, ability to professional development and professional activities, responsibility to themselves, employees and society, knowledge of innovative technologies, professional experience, professionalism, critical thinking);

- the strategic sphere of competencies (ability to make effective decisions, monitoring and analysis of the service provision quality, strategic thinking, strategic planning skills, ability to predict);

- personal competence (leadership, creativity, confidence, organizational ability, objectivity, patriotism, activity, flexibility, stress tolerance, optimism);

- communicative competence (skills of effective communication, business negotiations, possession of state and foreign languages, knowledge and possession of innovative technologies, ability to work in a team and organize its activities, conflict management);

- cognitive sphere of competencies (self-examination, self-awareness, self-improvement, self-control, self-regulation, positive self-perception, self-actualization, self-realization);

- effective sphere of competencies (responsibility for professional activity, ability to solve problem situations of professional activity, orientation towards achievement of goals, ability to systematically increase their competence, etc.).

Our analysis enables us to identify perspective ways of optimizing human resources in accordance with international concepts, normative acts on human development, the Strategy of the State Personnel Policy for 2012–2020 and the Strategies for the Development of Tourism and Resorts for the period up to 2026 that regulate the development and implementation of human resources in the tourist business environment. In particular, the updating of the legal framework of personnel policy, the improvement of a program of personnel development in the field of tourism, the formation of a competitive human resources potential in the tourist business environment, modernization of the system of professional training and providing a competent approach, the professionalization of personnel management departments of tourism, ensuring the formation and implementation of professional success of specialists activities in the field of tourism, the formation and improvement of the specialists professional culture in the field of tourism, optimization of staffing management tools in tourism sphere.

We believe that effective human resources policy in the tourism sphere of Ukraine should facilitate the professional growth of specialists, ensuring self-realization and professional development through the prism of implementation of innovative methods and practices for ensuring the competitiveness of human resources in the sphere of tourism. We are convinced that today we

need initiative, competent personnel with a new style of thinking and a vision of the tourism environment development that has democratic governance, the ability to operate in the current conditions of social development, be open to the introduction of relevant innovations that will ensure the formation of a competitive specialist in the field of tourism in Ukraine.

To summarize, the staffing of the tourism business should be aimed at forecasting and planning of the need for personnel, selection and placement of personnel in accordance with the competence level, creation of an effective human resources reserve, planning of personnel development, formation and implementation of a motivational component that will ensure the formation of a competitive human resource potential tourism sphere of Ukraine.

Conclusions. Thus, an effective human resources policy in the tourism sphere of Ukraine should facilitate the professional growth of specialists, ensuring self-realization and professional formation on the basis of the introduction of innovative methods and practices. The necessity of initiative, competent personnel with a new style of thinking and vision of the development of a tourism environment that possesses democratic methods of management, ability to act in the current conditions of social development, to be open to the introduction of appropriate innovations, which will ensure the formation of competitive human resources potential of tourism in Ukraine, is proved.

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КАДРОВИЙ ПОТЕНЦІАЛ СФЕРИ ТУРИЗМУ: СТАН, ВИКЛИКИ ТА ТЕНДЕНЦІ РОЗВИТКУ

У статті виокремлено та обґрунтовано стан і тенденції розвитку формування кадрового потенціалу сфери туризму. Доведено, що для оптимізації розвитку конкурентоздатного кадрового потенціалу сфери туризму в Україні потрібно передбачити прогнозування та планування потреби в кадрах, підбір і розстановку кадрів відповідно компетентнісного рівня, створення дієвого кадрового резерву, планування розвитку персоналу, формування і реалізацію мотиваційного компоненту. Охарактеризовано, що ефективна кадрова політика в сфері туризму України має сприяти професійному зростанню фахівців, забезпечуючи самореалізацію та успішність професійної діяльності. Обґрунтовано необхідність ініціативних, компетентних кадрів, з новим стилем мислення та баченням перспективи розвитку туристичного середовища, які володіють демократичними методами управління, здатність діяти в сучасних умовах суспільного розвитку, бути відкритими до впровадження відповідних новацій, що забезпечить формування конкурентоздатного кадрового потенціалу в умовах пошуку нової парадигми в сфері туризму в Україні. На основі отриманих результатів дослідження розроблено низку практичних рекомендацій з метою впровадження та реалізації ефективного управління кадровим ресурсом туристичного підприємства в Україні.

Ключові слова: кадровий потенціал, успішність, професійна діяльність, фахівець-туризмознавець, людські ресурси, конкурентоздатний фахівець, самореалізація, компетентнісний підхід, сфера туризму.

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